

TREX

Targeting Real chemical accuracy at the EXascale

TREX Blueprint

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Terminology

Abbreviation	Translation
CECAM	CENTRE EUROPÉEN DE CALCUL ATOMIQUE ET MOLÉCULAIRE
CINECA	CINECA CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE
CoE	CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE
DFT	DENSITY FUNCTIONAL THEORY
EU	EUROPEAN UNION
F2F	FACE-TO-FACE
HPC	HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPUTING
HPC3	HPC CENTER OF EXCELLENCE COUNCIL
HPDA	HIGH PERFORMANCE DATA ANALYTICS
KPI	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATOR
ML	MACHINE LEARNING
NCC	EUROPEAN NATIONAL COMPETENCE CENTERS
PRACE	PARTNERSHIP FOR ADVANCED COMPUTING IN EUROPE
Psi-k	AB INITIO (FROM ELECTRONIC STRUCTURE) CALCULATION OF COMPLEX PROCESS IN MATERIALS
QMC	QUANTUM MONTE CARLO
SISSA	INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL FOR ADVANCED STUDIES
TREX	TARGETING REAL CHEMICAL ACCURACY AT THE EXASCALE
UT	UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE
UVSQ	UNIVERSITÉ DE VERSAILLES-SAINT-QUENTIN-EN YVELINES
WP	WORK PACKAGE

Foreword

Welcome to this Blueprint of the TREX Center of Excellence (CoE) in Exascale Computing! To make a scientific impact, our journey brought together the communities of high-performance computing and high-accuracy quantum chemistry.

Within the fields of materials simulations and quantum chemistry, achieving the needed progress to optimally exploit future hardware resources has been a formidable challenge, and TREX has achieved significant advancements. In this Blueprint, you can read our achievements and our recommendations for policymakers, funding agencies, and national authorities to guide them on which priorities, challenges, and gaps should be addressed in the future.

The core of the TREX consortium comprises research institutions, universities, computing centres, and SMEs, whose expertise has been instrumental in driving our progress, with collaboration as our guiding principle. Whether you were a quantum chemist, a high-performance computing wizard, or an innovation seeker, TREX embraced you. Together, we collaborated, exchanged ideas, and pushed the different fields forward.

Our vision? Real chemical accuracy at the exascale. We envisioned simulating complex molecular interactions with unprecedented precision and speed. TREX aimed to make these visions tangible. The challenges have been many - algorithmic scalability, memory hierarchies, fault tolerance - but within these lay opportunities. TREX has developed novel algorithms and software solutions, and fostered interdisciplinary dialogues.

Keep exploring our demonstrators on energy, water, magnetism, and graphene. Dive into our publications, and re-listen or re-explore our events and their results. Take up and embed our TREX libraries TREXIO and QMckl. Use the enhanced TREX QMC flagship codes: NECI, GammCor, TurboRVB, CHAMP, QMC=Chem, and Quantum Package for material simulations. Contribute to our open source codes and share your insights. Together, we have contributed to the field of computational chemistry and high-performance computing software. We hope the scientific communities will continue to adopt the joint TREX results and build on our collaborative efforts.

Our deepest thanks to our dedicated team. We also express our gratitude to the European Commission for recognising the strategic significance of exascale computing for quantum chemistry and launching the call which founded our TREX Center of Excellence. We also hope that our recommendations will encourage the European Commission to sustain the efforts in this field.

Let us continue a legacy of excellence for high performance computing and quantum chemistry.

Jan Beerens and Prof. Claudia Filippi
Project Manager and Project Coordinator of TREX
University of Twente, The Netherlands

Contributing Authors & their Organisations

> The TREX Blueprint is based on the work of TREX key partners and experts who have worked together in the establishing and evolution of the TREX Centre of Excellence since its start in 2020. We would like to express our special thanks to the persons and organisations for bringing their vision, input and guidance into this community effort:

<p>Université de Versailles-Saint-Quentin-en-Yveline</p> <p>William Jalby (Principal Investigator), François Coppens, Pablo de Oliveira Castro, Salah Ibnamar, , Cédric Valensi</p>		
<p>Megware Computer Vertrieb und Service GmbH</p> <p>Axel Auweter (Principal Investigator), Kai Löhnig, Nico Mittenzwey</p>		
<p>Slovak Academy of Sciences</p> <p>Ivan Stich (Principal Investigator), Jan Brndiar, Yongda Huang</p>		
<p>Lodz University of Technology</p> <p>Kasia Pernal (Principal Investigator), Michal Hapka, Adam Sokół</p>		
<p>Trust-IT Services Srl</p> <p>Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Principal Investigator), Julie Arteza, Silvana Muscella, , Niccolò Zazzeri</p>		
<p>KTH Royal Institute of Technology (former partner)</p> <p>Dirk Pleiter (Principal Investigator), Rossen Apostolov, Johan Hellsvik, Joe Jordan, Daniel Medeiros, Szilárd Páll, , Alessandra Villa</p>		
	<p>University of Konstanz</p> <p>Thomas Bischoff (Principal Investigator)</p>	

Executive Summary

Quantum chemistry as accurate electronic structure methods have become an indispensable tool in chemistry, physics, biology, and materials science, and the arrival of exascale computers in the coming years has the potential to increase that utility even further. However, this potential will not be realized unless existing software is radically redesigned so that it can fully exploit the massively parallel architectures on which exascale computers are based.

In order to compete in the demanding rush in high-precision quantum chemical electronic structure simulation methods, between 2020 and 2024 the TREX Center of Excellence (CoE) federated European scientists, High Performance Computing (HPC) stakeholders, and SMEs to develop and apply high-performance software solutions for quantum mechanical simulations at the exascale. The final goal of the project was to develop a set of flagship Quantum Monte Carlo codes, able to exploit the capabilities of exascale computers at its highest.

The TREX project has undergone intense yet stimulating activities that we have wished to merge together as recommendations in this Blueprint. They result from constant and continued commitment from TREX partners who have collaborated in the establishing and evolving of the TREX Centre of Excellence since its start in 2020.

This Blueprint describes the main outcomes of TREX, its legacy for the HPC European ecosystem and the pathway that should be undertaken to ensure that QMC methods are exploited at most by contemporary HPC scientific and industry systems.

The Blueprint details the main TREX results, namely the quantum Monte Carlo and density matrix codes, the quantum Monte Carlo QMCKI library and the accrued interoperability between these codes thanks to the TREXIO library, fostering enhanced collaborations between groups that develop the same codes. The document also outlines the evolved pathway that should be undertaken to further develop QMC methods to ensure they are exploited at most by contemporary HPC scientific and industry systems.

In this context, a number of recommendations have been formulated and elaborated further in this Blueprint for policymakers, funding agencies such as the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU), and national authorities to guide them on which priorities, challenges, and gaps can be further addressed under Horizon Europe and the Digital Europe Programmes to foster wider access, usage, and uptake of knowledge of scalable eco-systems such as the one developed by TREX within an integrated HPC, HTC, and HPDA framework:

- **R1 - Ensure continued collaboration between HPC specialists and scientific researchers**
- **R2 - Promote open standards and open-source software**
- **R3 - Maintain a lively scientific network**
- **R4 - Keep on exploring collaboration with industry**
- **R5 - Focus on software (not just on hardware)**
- **R6 - Ensure longer research period for Horizon Europe funded projects**
- **R7 - Work on relevant real-world use cases**
- **R8 - Maintaining an international dialogue**

“European HPC can only be competitive at the global level through collaboration, joint dedication and shared motivation of the people behind it. This spirit, experienced by everyone in the TREX consortium, will not be forgotten.”

Axel Auweter, CTO and general manager, Megware

1. Introduction

Quantum Monte Carlo methods are cutting edge computational algorithms applied in quantum systems, allowing a large range of numerical simulations and providing, at the same time, extremely accurate results. QMC methods can twist the fate of modern research, allowing the gathering of results with incredible accuracy and speed, with the ultimate aim to overcome the need for experiments in labs.

Since its start in 2020, the TREX Center of Excellence (CoE) has federated European scientists, High Performance Computing (HPC) stakeholders, and SMEs to develop and apply high-performance software solutions for quantum mechanical simulations at the exascale. Over the last three years, the TREX flagship codes have undergone significant enhancements and demonstrated substantial improvements in various aspects. The code optimizations and parallelization techniques implemented have led to significant performance gains, enabling more efficient simulations and reducing the time required for calculations. The enhanced codes also exhibited improved scalability, allowing for simulations on larger systems and the exploration of more complex chemical and physical phenomena.

The technical challenges overcome by TREX both in quantum simulations and in HPC are of primary relevance for the worldwide scientific community and in particular for the **Quantum simulation of materials community, the Computational physicists and chemistry community, Hardware manufacturers and industrial players** (internal and external to TREX) working in the HPC industry will also be interested in reading the potential impact of QMC methods co-developed by TREX partners for the entire HPC sector.

The information included in this Blueprint aims at demonstrating how TREX has contributed to the development and evolution of the family of so-called **stochastic quantum chemistry methods** that are likely to play a major role in this redesign effort.

1.1 TREX in the context of European Supercomputing Policy

The TREX initiative was born in the wake of the establishment of the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU) in 2018 (becoming autonomous in the same year 2020 that TREX launched). The Joint Undertaking is a legal and funding entity with both public partners (EU, Member States, and Associated Partner States) and private partners (the European Technology Platform for High Performance Computing, the Big Data Value Association, and the European Quantum Industry Consortium).

The seven *billion* Euros allocated to the EuroHPC JU by its partners between 2021 and 2027 gives an idea of its importance in European policy, ranging from digital sovereignty with reliable, robust supply chains to support for policy objectives reflecting European values such as Green Computing. An appreciation for the structure and objectives of TREX goes through an understanding of the **structure and objectives of EuroHPC itself**, and is a useful prelude to an informed reading this Blueprint.

The applications of high-performance computing are vast, and the challenge of the EuroHPC partners was to structure the initiative in such a way as to create a **European supercomputing ecosystem** capable of serving all of its user communities in all of their needs for *applications, technologies, and skills*. They addressed this challenge by defining a set of four **Strategic R&I Intervention areas**, each building upon the next:

- > **Leadership in Use & Skills.** Competence Centres and training programmes in HPC commensurate with the labour market.
- > **Applications and Algorithms.** Centres of Excellence for HPC Applications and new algorithms for European exascale technology.
- > **European Software Stack.** Software and algorithms, programming models, and tools for exascale and post-exascale systems.
- > **European Open Hardware.** Ecosystem for the low power high-end general-purpose processor and accelerator.

Where is TREX positioned in these Strategic Intervention areas? We will see in the following that TREX covered *all* of the areas of strategic intervention defined by EuroHPC to various degrees, and begin to better understand both the purpose and the goals of TREX.

How is TREX involved in the first strategic area? EuroHPC has recognised that capacity-building is central to developing a robust labour market around HPC – a key part of a European supercomputing ecosystem. TREX committed a significant portion of its resources to **training** activities, particularly oriented to the next generation of researchers and practitioners.

How is TREX a Centre of Excellence? The Centres of Excellence are utilised in EuroHPC to support high-impact, high-profile application areas. The *specific* application area of TREX is chemistry, but the *broader* implications of TREX are for electronic structures in general, promising impact across a broad range of applications from medicine to materials design.

How are the TREX algorithms “high-profile”? An important policy objective of EuroHPC is to demonstrate the promise of the coming generation of exascale supercomputers. But for all the capabilities of supercomputers, not all application areas can truly take advantage of the so-called *convergence of high performance and high throughput*, where maximum speed and parallelism come together. That is where the Quantum Monte Carlo algorithms of TREX shine: their decomposition into massive numbers of relatively independent tasks allows them to take full advantage of concurrent execution and showcase the enormous power of the exascale computers. Indeed, one of the first applications intended for Europe’s first exascale computer (the *Jupiter* supercomputer in Jülich, Germany) is described by EuroHPC as “simulations for developing functional materials” – an application area of TREX. And so, by virtue of both its wide applicability and its unique characteristics for exascale computing, TREX will make a strong contribution to the goals of EuroHPC and help to lead the way to exascale computing.

Why is TREX involved in the European Software Stack? EuroHPC has recognized that advancing the algorithmic state of the art, while crucial, is not enough to ensure wide impact. Experience has shown that there are several technical and policy-related obstacles to practical take-up across supercomputing application communities. The development of high-performance computing software has proven to be devilishly difficult compared to traditional software engineering, often forcing the developers to engage directly with intricate parallel architectures, split their software into incomprehensible pieces, and try to validate that software with inadequate tools. The TREX emphasis on ensuring the simplicity of its flagship codes and the provision of well-structured libraries is a direct *technical* contribution to the EuroHPC strategic objective of a **European Software Stack**. The provision by TREX of its software in **open source** is a direct contribution to the European *policy* objective of promoting open source across all critical sectors as a means to ensure broad take-up of the software produced in initiatives like the European Software Stack in both research and commercial communities (especially SMEs). And, at the same time, it brings us full circle back to the overarching objectives of EuroHPC: open source is central to the strategy of achieving European digital sovereignty in all aspects of its IT infrastructure – including supercomputing capability.

Is TREX involved in the hardware-oriented Strategic Intervention Area? Although its major contribution is in the area of the European Software Stack, TREX has taken care to ensure that its results are presented whenever possible also in terms of their impact on future hardware architectures. For example, in view of the Joint Undertaking’s recent launching of several AI-related HPC initiatives, TREX researchers warn about the effects of GPUs associated with machine-learning on preserving the simplicity of the software codes. And finally, its *co-design* initiative, which involves users and their algorithms directly in the hardware design process, constitutes a unique TREX contribution to that last strategic intervention area defined by the EuroHPC JU.

In summary, the reader proceeding through subsequent sections of this document will see traces everywhere of the policy objectives of the Joint Undertaking described in this introduction, and will come to a deeper understanding of the many contributions made by TREX to the growth of a European supercomputing ecosystem.

2. TREX Key Exploitable Results: Software applications and infrastructure

The TREX project worked to develop a Centre of Excellence on high-accuracy quantum chemistry electronic structure and its main efforts were towards the development of an integrated HPC software platform of codes and libraries. In this context, the project featured the main Key Exploitable Results (KER) listed in the following paragraphs which are part of the service offerings portfolio and represent the main legacy of the TREX initiative¹.

2.1 TREX QMC flagship codes

The work of the TREX Centre of Excellence targeted eight different codes and libraries belonging to the scientific domain of quantum chemistry electronic structure, not all of them being exclusively QMC codes: **NECI**, **GammCor**, **TurboRVB**, **CHAMP**, **QMC=Chem**, **Quantum Package**, **TREXIO** and **QMCKI**. Over the last three years they have been modernised and refactored, and offered to the TREX stakeholders as unique high-performance codes to compute high-accuracy properties in quantum simulations of large systems. The QMC codes within TREX are at different stages of software development but are all algorithmically extremely advanced and uniquely powerful in the landscape of electronic structure methods.

2.1.1 NECI

Contributors

MPI-FKF, Stuttgart; University of Cambridge; King's College London

Audience

Quantum chemistry; materials science; biochemistry

NECI (<https://www2.fkf.mpg.de/alavi/neci/stable/index.html>) implements the full configuration interaction quantum Monte Carlo method, a particularly efficient formulation of full configuration interaction, which simulates molecular systems containing tens of electrons and obtains their properties, including energy spectra, density matrices, reaction pathways, etc. This can be combined with the transcorrelated method, implemented in the companion TCHInt library within the TREX project, to obtain chemically accurate results for a broader set of systems. NECI and TCHInt use standard four-body integrals produced by codes such as PySCF, Molpro, MolCAS, or VASP. The code is available under the GNU GPLv3 license, uses the HDF5 library for efficient input/output, and is parallelized with MPI, showing near-perfect scaling to tens of thousands of CPU cores.

Support for loading and saving one- and two-electron integrals in TREXIO format is now available in NECI via TCHInt.

2.1.2 GAMMCOR

Contributors

TUL (Lodz, Poland), University of Warsaw (Poland)

Audience

Theoretical chemistry community, quantum simulation of materials community

GammCor is an open-source program licensed under GNU GPLv3. It performs calculations of interaction energies using multireference symmetry adapted perturbation theory method (for ground and excited states), the adiabatic connection (AC and AC0) correlation energy for ground- and excited-state multireference wave functions, and range-separated multiconfiguration DFT energy with the long-range-AC/AC0 correlation correction. All the implemented multireference methods rely only on one- and two-electron reduced density matrices, which are computed externally.

GammCor has been adopted to cooperate with three widely used quantum chemistry packages: Molpro, Dalton, and Orca. Interoperability with other quantum chemistry codes has been enabled by interfacing GammCor with TREXIO library.

¹ Source: TREX D8.6 – TREX Draft Services Exploitation and Sustainability Plan

2.1.3 TurboRVB

Contributors

SISSA Scuola Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)

Audience

Computational physicists and chemists

TurboRVB is a package for ab initio QMC simulations of both molecular and bulk electronic systems. The code implements two types of well-established QMC algorithms: Variational Monte Carlo (VMC) and diffusion Monte Carlo in its robust and efficient lattice regularized variant. A key feature of the code is the possibility to use strongly correlated many-body wave functions, capable of describing several materials with very high accuracy, even when standard mean-field approaches such as density functional theory (DFT) fail.

The code implements the adjoint algorithmic differentiation that enables a very efficient evaluation of energy derivatives, comprising the ionic forces. Thus, one can perform structural optimizations and molecular dynamics in the canonical NVT ensemble at the VMC level, for both classical and quantum nuclei. For the electronic part, a full WF optimization (Jastrow and antisymmetric parts together) is made possible thanks to state-of-the-art stochastic algorithms for energy minimization. In the optimization procedure, the first guess can be obtained at the mean-field level by a built-in DFT driver.

The code has been efficiently parallelized by using a hybrid MPI-OpenMP protocol and already exploits rather efficiently GPU accelerators, that are currently available and nowadays used to reach the best computational performance in pre-exascale and future exascale HPC centres.

2.1.4 CHAMP

Contributors

University of Twente, SISSA Scuola Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati / Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)

The Cornell-Holland Ab-initio Materials Package (CHAMP) is an open-source code under the GPL-3.0 license. It is a quantum Monte Carlo code for electronic structure calculations of molecular and periodic systems. It has three basic capabilities, variational Monte Carlo, diffusion Monte Carlo, and optimization of many-body wave functions by energy minimization for ground and excited states. Noteworthy features of CHAMP are the compact formulation for a fast evaluation of multi-determinant expansions and their derivatives, the efficient computation of analytical interatomic forces, and the implementation of multiscale schemes for quantum Monte Carlo calculations. The code has been ported to supercomputers with different instruction set architectures with up to 200,000 CPU cores and an ideal strong scaling of up to 25,000 CPU cores.

2.1.5 QMC = CHEM

Contributors

Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)

Audience

Theoretical chemistry community

QMC=Chem is a quantum Monte Carlo package for electronic structure calculations of molecular systems. Its specificity is the ability to handle very large multi-determinant expansions, close to full configuration interaction, at the variational Monte Carlo (VMC) and diffusion Monte Carlo (DMC) levels. The code is available under the GNU GPLv3 license and has been used with up to 70 000 of CPU cores.

2.1.6 Quantum Package

Contributors

Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)

Audience

Theoretical chemistry community, quantum simulation of materials community

Quantum Package is an electronic structure software focused on wave function methods (configuration interaction) combined with density functional theory. It allows estimating full configuration interaction energies with the CIPSI algorithm, and provides a friendly environment for the development of new methods. The code is available under the GNU AGPL license and has shown a good scalability with up to 20 000 CPU cores.

2.2 TREX Libraries

Within the TREX project, state-of-the-art programs for quantum Monte Carlo (QMC) calculations have been analysed to identify key algorithms to be then implemented in human-readable, open-source software QMCKI & TREXIO libraries. The libraries have been further optimized for future exascale supercomputers by computer scientists of the TREX project.

2.2.1 The QMC kernel library (QMCKI)

Contributors

Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), University of Twente (UT), SISSA Scuola Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati, Université de Versailles Saint-Quentin (UVSQ), CINECA

Audience

Theoretical chemistry community, quantum simulation of materials community.

The high-performance QMC kernel library (QMCKI) developed within the framework of the TREX project addresses CPU-intensive tasks common to various QMC algorithms and implementations. It was finally delivered in two versions, a human-readable one to facilitate future developments and a high-performance one tailored to different architectures. It is based on an open-source development model to facilitate the uptake by commercial codes and allow stakeholders to provide revised versions to the final users.

The QMCKI library is dedicated to the implementation of the essential kernels inherent to Quantum Monte Carlo (QMC) techniques. Its methodology of development adheres to the principle of separation of concerns: in an ideal setting, researchers and method developers in scientific domains should not be burdened by the intricacies of system architecture. Conversely, IT specialists and research engineers in HPC should direct their efforts towards the optimization of mathematical libraries and system-level components. TREX worked to emphasise the delineation of the API, development of tests, and a pedagogical exposition of the primary algorithms of QMC methods. TREX specialists in HPC utilised this repository as a guide for crafting optimized versions of the functions originally proposed in the pedagogical version of the library.

The Quantum Monte Carlo Kernel Library has been ported to GPU. To this end, a separate and independent library, `qmckl_gpu`, has been created in order to provide kernels specifically optimized for GPU porting. Both the OpenMP offload and OpenACC paradigms have been used to provide a wide portability across different architectures. A dedicated effort has been deployed, in collaboration with experts from Nvidia, to profile and optimize the most time-consuming kernels in the atomic orbitals (AO) and molecular orbitals (MO) parts of the library. The offloaded kernels have been then benchmarked on the CINECA's supercomputers (Marconi100, Leonardo booster) and on the Lumi supercomputer, with the allocation time granted by an EuroHPC Development Access Call (No. EHPC-DEV-2023D06-036).

2.2.2 TREXIO

Contributors

Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), University of Twente (UT), SISSA Scuola Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati

Audience

Theoretical chemistry community, quantum simulation of materials community.

The input/output library (TRESIO) was released to efficiently handle communication between codes within and outside TRES. It features a developer-friendly front-end interface and can handle various types of file formats as a back end. It is equipped with interfaces to well-established quantum chemistry simulation codes.

TRESIO is an open-source file format and library specifically developed for the storage and manipulation of data generated by quantum chemistry calculations. It serves as a reliable and efficient method for storing and exchanging wave function parameters and matrix elements, making it an essential tool for researchers in the field of quantum chemistry, beyond the TRES CoE. The creation of a standardized data format was crucial to enable seamless data migration and compatibility among different flagship codes within the TRES platform.

2.3 Integration of the QMCKI and TRESIO libraries into a TRES platform

The high-performance platform of libraries and interoperable TRES QMC and deterministic (Quantum Package, Gammcor) codes, provisioned with machine learning tools, and integrated within the AiiDA informatics infrastructure² for workload management and HTC, resulted in a flexible, open, and inclusive platform for software development, which will act as a nucleation center for the communities in quantum chemical and material science simulations at the exascale.

The integration of the QMCKI and TRESIO libraries into the flagship codes further enhanced the capabilities of the codes. The QMCKI library provided advanced numerical algorithms and techniques that significantly improved the efficiency of the simulations. The TRESIO library ensured seamless data exchange and compatibility among the codes, eliminating potential data format inconsistencies and simplifying the overall data management process, enhancing collaboration and promoting interoperability within the TRES platform.

2 <https://www.aaiida.net/>

3. TREX legacy and benefits for the wider HPC community

TREX has definitely increased the awareness of the ultra-accurate QMC stochastic methods in the electronic structure community in Europe. TREX generated Key Exploitable results which are expected to last for years, perhaps decades and they are bound to strongly affect the development of the QMC community and electronic structure community as a whole in the future. Via training and education, a new generation of young people with expertise in QMC methods and large-scale computing was created, trained and knowledgeable in scientific research QMC applications as well as in the HPC development methodologies. Last but not least, as a result of the expertise provided by the TREX partners, a range of very valuable scientific results and papers was generated.

The TREX initiative has demonstrated that the task of adapting computational codes to contemporary HPC systems, particularly those with GPU accelerators, is far more complex than what is often suggested by HPC vendors. While these systems offer remarkable computational capabilities, fully harnessing their power without compromising code simplicity remains a formidable challenge. While CPU compiler technology has made strides in facilitating hardware optimization without complicating the source code, the introduction of GPUs often reverses this progress. It necessitates a level of hardware and system programming expertise that many scientists find extraneous to their primary research objectives.

The key results of the TREX project can be summarised as follows:

1. Optimization of the existing **quantum Monte Carlo and density matrix codes**, and creation of a quantum Monte Carlo library which can be linked to make any numerical code QMC capable (in principle);
2. Porting these codes to **HPC architectures**, by making some of them (e.g. TurboRVB) GPU accelerated;
3. **Accrued interoperability** between these codes thanks to the TREXIO library, fostering enhanced collaborations between groups that develop the same codes;
4. **Scientific achievements** (e.g. accurate determination of the phase diagram of high pressure hydrogen) that would not have been possible without the code optimization and code porting described in points 1) and 2);
5. **Feeding communities of young scientists with a “quantum Monte Carlo culture”**, making them aware of the appealing features of a stochastic way of approaching the many-body problem in quantum physics and chemistry, achieved with the organisation of several schools)

These results outline the pathway that should be undertaken to further evolve the QMC methods to ensure they are exploited at most by contemporary HPC scientific and industry system, to develop applications capable of responding to today’s scientific big data challenges in applied research fields such as water, layered materials, hydrogen storage, polymorphism, high-pressure phase diagrams, high-temperature superconductors and more.

In the sections below we have collected an analysis of the main pathways for ensuring that the results achieved by the TREX process and the efforts undertaken to adapt computational codes to contemporary HPC resources are actually implemented in the near future.

3.1 Enhancing capabilities of research institutes

The TREX project’s contributions to QMC simulations offer a substantial enhancement to the European research institutes’ capabilities. This is the case for instance for the institutes directly engaged in the TREX project, such as CNRS (Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique), the Sorbonne University, the Max Planck Institute, the University of Twente, the Slovak Academy of Sciences, CINECA, SISSA, the Lodz University of Technology, the University of Konstanz.

The tools and methodologies emanating from the TREX project are prime candidates for incorporation into educational curricula, affording students the opportunity for practical engagement with cutting-edge computational methods. By assembling a multidisciplinary team of experts, the TREX project created an environment conducive to cross-disciplinary research.

“Open science and open-source software are crucial for advancing knowledge and innovation. By sharing research openly, we accelerate scientific discovery and learning. Open-source software allows for collaborative improvements, ensuring tools are more reliable and accessible. This approach not only fosters transparency in research but also builds a global community of scientists and developers, working together for the greater good.”

Anthony Scemama, Senior Research Engineer at CNRS and TREX leader of WP1 dedicated to Implement a human-readable version of the library (QMCKI) with the standard API

The deployment of TRES improved codes is fundamental to carry out quantum Monte Carlo calculations and study the physical/chemical properties of the targeted systems (water, layered materials, hydrogen storage, polymorphism, high-pressure phase diagrams, high-temperature superconductors), at the edge of nowadays research. This is the case of the quantum theory of materials group in the IMPMC institute at Sorbonne University.

“An ambitious project we have is to develop an extensive database of machine learning potentials derived from accurate quantum Monte Carlo calculations for an accelerated materials discovery. This will be done in collaboration with other scientists at the IMPMC expert in machine-learning methods, and by exploiting a cross-fertilizing scheme where QMC plays the role of generator of accurate training sets. In this frame, the Aida integration will be very useful. As an additional future plan, we would like to extend the work done in TRES towards a machine learning representation of the correlated wave functions from first principles”.

Michele Casula, Head of the “Quantum Theory of Materials” (TQM) group at the IMPMC, CNRS

MaxPlanck Institute also confirmed that they will continue the development of the NECI code and the associated trans-correlation library TCHInt with a group of 5 people in the Institute for Solid State Research who will continue working on this as a legacy of TRES.

Utilising the refined flagship codes and the QMCKI library will facilitate more precise and computationally efficient predictions of molecular properties. These research outcomes hold the **potential for publication in prestigious scientific journals**, thereby bolstering institutes’ standing in the domains of quantum chemistry and high-performance computing. The effective realization and utilization of the TRES project’s deliverables and publications could act as a robust cornerstone for securing **future research grants**, thereby ensuring the sustained viability of TRES research activities.

Last but not least, the effective realisation and utilisation of the TRES project’s deliverables could act as a robust cornerstone for securing future research grants, thereby ensuring the sustained viability of research activities.

3.2 Exploitation of the next generation of European supercomputers

The optimised codes and libraries developed under the TRES initiative present a **compelling opportunity for cloud-based deployment**. By offering QMC simulation services via a cloud platform, the project could extend its reach to a broader scientific community, encompassing both academic research institutes and industrial entities. This cloud-based service model not only democratises access to high-level computational tools but also opens up a potential revenue stream that could further sustain and expand the project’s impact.

This was the case, for instance, of CINECA HPC machines. The Quantum Monte Carlo Kernel Library (QMCKI) has been ported to GPU by CINECA in collaboration with UVSQ. To this end, a separate and independent library, qmckl_gpu, has been created in order to provide kernels specifically optimized for GPU porting. Both the openMP offload and openACC paradigms have been used to provide a wide portability across different architectures. A dedicated effort has been deployed by CINECA, in collaboration with experts from Nvidia, to profile and optimise the most time-consuming kernels in the atomic orbitals (AO) and molecular orbitals (MO) parts of the library. The offloaded kernels have been then benchmarked on the CINECA’s clusters (Marconi100, Leonardo booster) and on the Lumi supercomputer (in collaboration with UVSQ), with the allocation time granted by an EuroHPC Development Access Call (No. EHPC-DEV-2023D06-036).

3.3 Growing a trained community of Quantum Monte Carlo experts

Increasing the expertise of the wider community in both the scientific application of the software and its efficient HPC usage is a fundamental part of the impact of TRES work. Training activities have been one of the main instruments for achieving the desired impact of our results.

The TRES community is not large but growing and quite precious. Different stakeholders were trained via TRES:

- Postdocs and PhD students directly trained in the groups participating in TRES CoE
- More than 250 participants of the various schools and workshops organised by TRES ([Webinars](#), [Schools](#), [Workshops](#), [Hackathons](#)).

The QMC community is small when compared to the broad quantum chemistry and density functional community, in part because in these other communities the codes and approaches are easier to use and often less computationally demanding. QMC codes require more expertise and are computationally intensive. Therefore, there is a compelling need for stimulating researchers to keep on doing scientific research that requires or can be better performed by exploiting QMC methods.

Thanks to a continuous training activity, TREX acknowledged a **steady increase in the numbers of QMC method practitioners** to which the TREX project has contributed considerably. The viable stochastic sampling algorithms able to take the full advantage of the current heterogeneous HPC architectures, combined with accessibility of the hardware improving over time paint a bright future for the QMC methods. The same happened with DFT methods which might have looked expensive 30 years ago in comparison to the tight-binding methods often used then for electronic structure calculation, whereas they are regarded as state-of-the-art “cheap” methods nowadays.

QMC methods require a qualified expertise to be able to get the most out of them. Collaborative efforts are therefore strongly recommended between the principal developers and the users of the codes. Ensuring awareness about the collaborative effort and experience needed to develop and run the codes might be a challenge, mainly looking at communities other than those involved in TREX. Tutorials are not enough, closed collaborative writing and evolving of the codes is fundamental. Maintenance is also a collaborative effort.

Ensuring collaboration is not so easy and it is a prime responsibility of the Principal Investigators of each code. Considerable expertise is required, so the knowledge acquired within TREX is precious and should be kept and brought forward. A lot of the experts come from communities where the codes are much more simple to deploy, and it might not be so clear how difficult and complicated it was (and is) to have these codes effectively running.

“Only by continuing to promote a lively scientific network, it will be possible to involve the trained people in new projects and to leverage on their skills.”

Michele Casula, Head of the “Quantum Theory of Materials” (TQM) group at the IMPMC, CNRS

The QMC community should look at the **new generation to attract new brains and human resources**, for a restless improvement of its tools and algorithms. Leveraging the skills acquired through the TREX project’s training activities can be approached via the establishment of a mentorship program where those who have undergone training can guide newcomers in both the scientific and high-performance computing aspects of the software. This not only reinforces the skills of the mentors but also accelerates the learning curve for new users, creating a virtuous cycle of knowledge transfer. Furthermore, those who have been trained could contribute to the development of online courses, webinars, or tutorials aimed at a wider audience. This would not only disseminate the knowledge more broadly but also establish the TREX project as thought leaders in the field.

Another aspect to consider is the skills acquired by the trained QMC experts during TREX on efficiency in high performance software. With hundreds of terawatt hours of electricity spent on ICT technology annually and an unstoppable growth in digitalisation, performance and energy efficiency in software is one of the key factors in meeting our global sustainability goals. While the TREX use cases were QMC-specific, many of the skills can easily be transferred to other application domains by the people trained. There will be a tremendous need for experts on efficiency in high performance software for years to come.

3.4 Opportunities for industry uptake

The potential uptake of TREX inter-operable QMC codes for exascale application in the European HPC Industry, driving the installation of the new pre-exascale or exascale computers, is one of the key exploitation channels that was investigated by the project, considering that the performance and efficiency of HPC applications largely depend on the matching of algorithms with HPC hardware.

The TREX project’s outcomes offer valuable insights into the intricacies of optimising QMC simulations for HPC environments. These findings have several implications that could be highly beneficial for HPC industry and commercial providers. Firstly, the TREX project serves as a real-world testbed for evaluating the performance and limitations of current HPC hardware, particularly when dealing with complex algorithms like those used in QMC simulations. This provides HPC vendors with invaluable data to improve their hardware offerings, making them more compatible with the computational demands of advanced scientific research. Secondly, the project’s focus on co-design—integrating the needs of end-users and their algorithms into the hardware development process—offers a blueprint for how future HPC systems should be developed. By adopting a co-design approach, HPC providers can create systems that are not just powerful but also user-friendly, thereby widening their market appeal to include scientists who may not be HPC experts.

“I am convinced that QMC sets the only viable computational paradigm for truly large-scale electronic structure computing. The difference lies in (nearly independent) stochastic sampling algorithms vs. large matrix diagonalization which all the other methods of DFT and quantum chemistry are doing.”

Ivan Štich, Professor of Physics, Slovenská akadémia vied

The QMC codes used in TREX have the potential to run efficiently on a large variety of computing architectures beyond classical HPC clusters (e.g. HTC clusters, cloud environments, etc). With the project's success in implementing consolidated routines such as the QMckl and TREXIO library, porting and optimization of the codes for upcoming HPC hardware generations will be greatly facilitated. All Monte Carlo applications will remain at the forefront of use cases for next-generation HPC systems due to their embarrassingly parallel nature. In addition, the work performed in the field of automated workflows leveraging the AiiDA framework will serve as a great reference for wider HPC adoption and integration in complex environments such as, for example, digital twins.

Having relevant real-world use cases on the largest HPC systems turned out to be crucial in continuing to make proper business cases for buying and operating such large HPC clusters. The progress made in QMC simulations through the TREX project could indeed offer invaluable contributions to a range of industrial sectors, including but not limited to pharmaceuticals, materials science, and energy production. The refined computational methodologies and algorithms could facilitate more accurate modelling and prediction in these industries, thereby accelerating the pace of innovation and potentially leading to breakthroughs in drug discovery, material design, and energy efficiency.

Collaboration with industry partners can also be a fruitful avenue. Those trained in the TREX project could serve as liaisons or consultants for industries that could benefit from QMC simulations, such as pharmaceuticals or materials science. Their specialised knowledge would be invaluable in translating academic advancements into practical applications.

Beyond two highly relevant computational libraries and the adoption of world-class community codes to use them, TREX managed to bridge DFT and QMC approaches with seamless compatibility of information.

"A machine learning approach to the QMC will revolutionise the way QMC is perceived. If QMC will become a reliable "training set generator" machine learning can project it to a much wider applicability range and it will make QMC as efficient as DFT, or as fast as any atomistic potential, but with the advantage of yielding more accurate potentials than DFT itself."

Michele Casula, Head of the "Quantum Theory of Materials" (TQM) group at the IMPMC, CNRS

3.5 Scientific publications

The TREX consortium published 35 peer-reviewed articles in prestigious journals such as Nature Physics, Nature Communications, Physical Review Research, Science Advances, Physical Review B and more.

In April 2023, TREX successfully published a scientific article titled "Quantum Phase Diagram of High-Pressure Hydrogen" in **Nature Physics** (Monacelli, L., Casula, M., Nakano, K. *et al.* Quantum phase diagram of high-pressure hydrogen. *Nat. Phys.* 19, 845–850 (2023). The work has also been leveraging Sandro Sorella's research activities over the past years, being one of his posthumous papers he co-authored. This Nature Physics publication highlights the vital role that theoretical physics and computational methods play together in advancing scientific understanding. The article's success is a testament to the team's dedication and expertise, as well as the fundamental contribution that TREX project has been able to produce in such a research. Indeed, **the computational experience that the team gained in the context of the TREX project, and especially the QMC methods developed and optimized within TREX, were crucial to lead to the highest levels of accuracy and predictability.**

The publication of TREXIO in the **Journal of Chemical Physics** (*J. Chem. Phys.* 158, 174801 (2023)), in May 2023 has attracted considerable scholarly focus, as evidenced by its elevated Research Interest Score on ResearchGate. Moreover, research groups external to the TREX consortium have begun to integrate TREXIO into their workflows to enhance interoperability with other software. The adoption of TREXIO will continue to grow, ultimately establishing it as the de facto standard for wave function data storage.

TREX publications are available from the TREX public website (<https://trex-coe.eu/publications>).

4. Sustainable paths for the future: TREX recommendations

The enhancements in computational accuracy and efficiency achieved by the TREX project could serve as a case study for shaping policy decisions. Specifically, these advancements could guide the allocation of research funding and strategic focus in the interconnected domains of computational chemistry and high-performance computing. By demonstrating the tangible benefits of optimised QMC simulations, the project advocates for increased investment and attention in these critical scientific fields.

Below we have listed 8 recommendations for policy stakeholders to advise them on which priorities, challenges, and gaps can be further addressed when defining future priority calls under the EuroHPC, Horizon Europe and Digital Europe Programmes.

R1 - Ensure continued collaboration between HPC specialists and scientific researchers

While CPU compiler technology has made strides in facilitating hardware optimization without complicating the source code, the introduction of GPUs often reverses this progress. It necessitates a level of hardware and system programming expertise that many scientists find extraneous to their primary research objectives. This state of affairs underscores the need for ongoing collaboration between HPC specialists and scientific researchers, particularly given the relative immaturity of the existing software stack, which includes compilers, libraries, and debugging tools. In Europe, we have researchers in laboratories and computer scientists in Supercomputing centres, but they are not able to efficiently work together because they have different projects and priorities. One recommendation could be to make researchers working on code inside HPC centres to boost alignment and collaboration on identified research cases.

R2 - Promote open standards and open-source software

GPU manufacturers often push their proprietary solutions as industry standards. This creates challenges for users, especially with proprietary languages like Cuda. While alternatives like OpenMP or SYCL exist, they currently fall short in efficiently utilising accelerators due to inadequate support from GPU manufacturers in refining the user experience. **There is a growing need among users for a fully open-source software stack for programming various accelerators, akin to what gcc offers for CPUs, without relying on any proprietary elements.**

R3 - Maintain a lively scientific network

Establishing a **mentorship program** where those who have undergone training can guide newcomers in both the scientific and high-performance computing aspects of the software will not only reinforce the skills of the mentors but also accelerate the learning curve for new users, creating a virtuous cycle of knowledge transfer. Furthermore, those who have been trained could contribute to the development of online courses, webinars, or tutorials aimed at a wider audience, as well as be engaged in new projects and to leverage on their skills.

R4 - Keep on exploring collaboration with industry

Collaboration with industry partners proved to be a fruitful avenue to continue to be exploited. The people trained in the TREX project could serve as liaisons or consultants for industries that could benefit from QMC simulations, such as pharmaceuticals or materials science. Their specialised knowledge would be invaluable in translating academic advancements into practical applications.

R5 - Invest in Machine Learning

For some specific research and industry sectors, for instance dedicated to develop new materials with targeted functionalities, the recommendation is to invest in machine learning interfaced with QMC codes able to produce accurate dataset “in silico” (without performing more expensive experiments in the laboratories). The world needs practical, operational applications leading to scientific and societal impact, and the efforts should concentrate on producing QMC applications useful for the broader condensed matter community. Machine Learning is a large part of the future, the recommendation is to invest to make QMC able to adapt to this community.

R6 - Ensure longer research periods for Horizon Europe-funded projects

The TREX COE suffered from its short time frame for implementation (42 months). Continuity of the research is the main issue since a three-year period is too short to deliver both computational and research results.

Although the need for continuous investments on infrastructures has been formally recognised by EuroHPC, and the value of CoEs recognised, the model of short-term Centres of Excellence doesn't seem to convince the scientific community. There are multiple CoEs which continued from the previous EC funding programmes and are now under the EuroHPC funding mechanisms. There is space for continuity as long as good proposals are presented. Nonetheless, ensuring longer funding periods - of 5 to 10 years - for Centres of Excellence such as TREX would increase their impact, allow for more results, and meet the need of periodically allowing QMC codes to adapt to the relatively short lifetime of HPC machines. Teaching students how to code and how to perform cutting edge research cannot be done in a three-year timeframe.

R7 - Work on relevant real-world use cases

The applications of supercomputing in science are countless: from fundamental physics (advancing the frontiers of knowledge of matter or exploring the universe) to materials science (designing new critical components for the pharmaceutical or energy sectors) and earth science (modelling the atmospheric and oceanic phenomena at planetary level). TREX demonstrators focused on magnetism, surface physics, layered materials, energy excitations, and high-pressure hydrogen.

Having relevant real-world use cases on the largest HPC systems is crucial in continuing to make proper business cases for buying and operating such large HPC clusters. This is also in line with the objectives of EuroHPC to support strategic European Union initiatives such as the Destination Earth initiative and the development of applications for the creation of a Digital Twin of the Earth and the continuous calls to be launched for European projects developing applications in areas not yet covered.

R8 - Maintaining an international dialogue

Europe and the US have a long history of QMC cooperation, dating back to the 70s, which keeps on ensuring fruitful knowledge exchange. The scientific and research cooperation benefits from student and staff exchanges between the two regions (as well as Asia) and is inspiring a positive competition which is strategic for boosting development in the HPC framework. That said, differences exist concerning funding duration and emphasis. The US ensures longer research programmes - and models. The US supports HPC centres and supercomputing machines, while Europe has a long history of funding mechanisms for software development - which at the same time are a source of complementarity while introducing some barriers in the practical implementation of continued cooperation. The recommendation in this case is for the funding agencies to continue offering cooperation opportunities for the QMC communities across the Atlantic to jointly train students, fellows and developers, share HPC resources, and facilitate liaison moments between computational scientists and developers for different codes and application areas.

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